

Efficient Management of Medical Image Databases, Based on Inverse Pyramid Decomposition

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Abstract

In the paper is presented one new approach for efficient and flexible management of medical databases with multi-layer access, based on the Inverse Pyramid Decomposition (IPD). The IPD offers various tools for multi-layer transfer of the processed visual information with consecutively quality improvement, together with reliable content protection ensured by resistant and fragile watermarks and data hiding. The proposed approach permits the insertion of multiple watermarks in same file. Besides, for some access levels part of the visual information is hidden (for example, some specific regions of interest in the medical images) and could be revealed by authorized users only. The general part of the database information could be used for various applications: students learning, disease description, disease history and treatment, statistics information, etc.

Keywords: Medical image databases, Management of image databases, Image content protection.

1 Introduction

Large multimedia databases (MD) are increasingly important part of computer and information sciences. One of the most important contemporary implementations is the development of Electronic medical health records (EMHR), which contain wide variety of multimedia objects (images, electronic documents, video, audio, etc.). The management of such databases should satisfy contradictory requirements: easy and reliable access, content protection, and many others. Additional important requirements arose concerning the feature extraction, quality level, and information filtering. In spite of the already performed work in image and audio processing, image analysis and pattern recognition are still not adequately addressed. The usual approach in the contemporary practice is to use Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) standard [Camapum et al, 2009]: the images are compressed and stored and their accessibility and content protection depends on the MD management. In medicine to date, virtually all picture archive and communication systems (PACS) retrieve images simply by indices based on patient name, technique, or some observer-coded text of diagnostic findings [Huang,1991; Alsen et al, 2003]. There are a number of uses for medical image databases, each of which would make different requirements on database organization. Classification of images into named or coded diagnostic categories may suffice for retrieving groups of images for teaching purposes. One of the most powerful contemporary tools for image archiving is the JPEG2000 image-compression standard, which offers many features that support interactive access to large images [Taubman and Marcellin, 2002; JPEG2000 standard, 2003] (high-efficiency compression, resolution scalability, quality scalability, and spatial random access). The main disadvantage is that JPEG2000 does not offer tools for layered content protection and access.

In the paper is presented one new approach for flexible management of medical image databases with multi-layer access, based on the Inverse Pyramid Decomposition (IPD), which offers various tools for layered transfer of the processed visual information with consecutively quality improvement, together with reliable content protection with resistant and fragile watermarks. Besides, for some access levels part of the information is hidden, such as: personal patients' data, some specific regions of interest (ROI) in the corresponding medical images, etc., and could be revealed by authorized users only. The IPD decomposition offers lower computational complexity than the JPEG 2000 standard, together with instant ROI accessibility and image content protection.

The paper is arranged as follows: In Section 2 is presented the main idea of the IPD decomposition; in Section 3 is described the method for multi-layer watermarking and data hiding; in Section 4 is presented the approach for the database management, and Section 5 contains the Conclusions.

2 Basic Principles of the IPD Decomposition

The 2D matrix $[B]$, which corresponds to a digital image, could be represented using the Inverse Pyramid Decomposition (IPD) (Kountchev and Kountcheva, 2008). For this, the matrix is first divided into blocks of size $2^n \times 2^n$. The corresponding sub-matrix for each block $[B(2^n)]$ is then decomposed in accordance with the relation:

$$[1] \quad [B(2^n)] = [\tilde{B}_0(2^n)] + \sum_{p=1}^r [\tilde{E}_{p-1}(2^n)] + [R(2^n)], \text{ for } r < n-1,$$

where the number of decomposition components is $(r+2)$. Here $[R(2^n)]$ is a residual component, which is equal to zero for $r = n - 1$. Each component in Eq. [1] is a matrix of size $2^n \times 2^n$, corresponding to the decomposition layer p .

The *First decomposition component*, $[\tilde{B}_0(2^n)]$ calculated for the layer $p = 0$, is a coarse approximation of the block $[B(2^n)]$. It is obtained through 2D inverse orthogonal transform (OT) of the block $[\tilde{S}'_0(2^n)]$ in correspondence with the relation:

$$[2] \quad [\tilde{B}_0(2^n)] = [T_0(2^n)]^{-1} [\tilde{S}'_0(2^n)] [T_0(2^n)],$$

where $[T_0(2^n)]^{-1}$ is the matrix of the 2D OT, $[\tilde{S}'_0(2^n)]$, of size $2^n \times 2^n$;

$$[3] \quad [\tilde{S}'_0(2^n)] = FQ_0^{-1} \{ [S_0(2^n)] \} = FQ_0^{-1} \{ FQ_0 \{ [S_0(2^n)] \} \}.$$

$FQ_0 \{ \bullet \}$ and $FQ_0^{-1} \{ \bullet \}$ are correspondingly the operators for filtration and quantization of $[S_0(2^n)]$ and for dequantization of $[\tilde{S}'_0(2^n)]$ in the decomposition layer $p = 0$. In result of the operation, performed by $FQ_0 \{ \bullet \}$, are selected and quantized the pre-selected high-energy coefficients in the matrix $[S_0(2^n)]$, which define $[\tilde{S}'_0(2^n)]$. In result of the performance of the inverse operator $FQ_0^{-1} \{ \bullet \}$ and after the inverse operation, represented in Eq. [2], is calculated the component $[\tilde{B}_0(2^n)]$. The term $[S_0(2^n)]$ in Eq. [3] is calculated after direct 2D OT of the matrix $[B(2^n)]$, i.e.:

$$[4] \quad [S_0(2^n)] = [T_0(2^n)] [B(2^n)] [T_0(2^n)].$$

Here $[T_0(2^n)]$ is the matrix for 2D OT, of size $2^n \times 2^n$, which could be of any kind: (DFT, DCT, KLT, etc.), and whose inverse matrix is $[T_0(2^n)]^{-1}$.

The remaining decomposition components from Eq. [1] are the approximating matrices $[\tilde{E}_p(2^{n-p})]$ for decomposition levels $p = 1, 2, \dots, r$. These matrices comprise the sub-matrices $[\tilde{E}_p^{k_p}(2^{n-p})]$, of size $2^{n-p} \times 2^{n-p}$ for $k_p = 1, 2, \dots, 4^p$, obtained as a result of the quad-tree division of $[\tilde{E}_p(2^{n-p})]$. Each sub-matrix $[\tilde{E}_p^{k_p}(2^{n-p})]$ is defined as:

$$[5] \quad [\tilde{E}_{p-1}^{k_p}(2^{n-p})] = [T_p(2^{n-p})]^{-1} [\tilde{S}_p^{k_p}(2^{n-p})] [T_p(2^{n-p})]^{-1} \text{ for } k_p = 1, 2, \dots, 4^p,$$

where 4^p is the number of the quad-tree branches in the decomposition level p ;

$[T_p(2^{n-p})]^{-1}$ is a matrix of size $2^{n-p} \times 2^{n-p}$ in the decomposition level p , used for the inverse 2D OT;

$$[6] \quad [\tilde{S}_p^{k_p}(2^{n-p})] = FQ_p^{-1} \{ [\tilde{S}_p^{k_p}(2^{n-p})] \} = FQ_p^{-1} \{ FQ_p \{ [S_p^{k_p}(2^{n-p})] \} \};$$

$FQ_p \{ \bullet \}$ and $FQ_p^{-1} \{ \bullet \}$ are correspondingly the operators for filtration and quantization of $[S_p^{k_p}(2^{n-p})]$ and for dequantization of $[\tilde{S}_p(2^n)]$ in the layer p .

Each transform is defined by the equation:

$$[7] \quad [S_p^{k_p}(2^{n-p})] = [T_p(2^{n-p})] [E_{p-1}^{k_p}(2^n)] [T_p(2^{n-p})], \text{ where}$$

$[T_p(2^{n-p})]$ is a matrix of size $2^{n-p} \times 2^{n-p}$ in the level p for each block $[E_{p-1}^{k_p}(2^{n-p})]$ when $k_p = 1, 2, \dots, 4^p$ in the difference matrix, defined by the relation:

$$[8] \quad [E_{p-1}(2^{n-p})] = \begin{cases} [B(2^n)] - [\tilde{B}_0(2^n)] & \text{for } p = 1; \\ [E_{p-2}(2^{n-p})] - [\tilde{E}_{p-2}(2^{n-p})] & \text{for } p = 2, 3, \dots, r. \end{cases}$$

In result of the decomposition (Eq. [1]) for each block $[B(2^n)]$ are defined the following spectrum coefficients:

- from the level $p = 0$ - all non-zero coefficients in $[\tilde{S}'_0(2^n)]$;
- from levels $p = 1, 2, \dots, r$ - all non-zero coefficients $[\tilde{S}_p^{k_p}(2^{n-p})]$ for $k_p = 1, 2, \dots, 4^p$.

The spectrum coefficients of same spatial frequency from all image sub-blocks are arranged in common massifs in accordance with the decomposition level, p and losslessly coded.

3 Resistant Watermarking, Based on 2D-CHT

The watermark data is inserted in the phases of selected spectrum coefficients, obtained with 2D Complex Hadamard Transform (2D-CHT) with "arranged" complex Hadamard matrix for the image matrix $[B(N)]$ (Kountchev et al, 2010).

3.1 Watermark Embedding

The image matrix $[B(2^n)]$ of size $N \times N$ ($N = 2^n$) is first processed with direct 2D-CHT:

$$[9] \quad [S(2^n)] = [CH(2^n)][B(2^n)][CH(2^n)].$$

Here $[S(2^n)]$ is the matrix of the discrete image spectrum; $[CH(2^n)]$ - arranged matrix, defined by the natural complex Hadamard matrix $[CH_0(2^n)]$ with elements:

$$[10] \quad ch_0(t, q) = j^{tq} h_0(t, q) \text{ for } t, q = 0, 1, \dots, 2^n - 1,$$

$$h_0(t, q) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } n=2; \\ \sum_{i=0}^n \left\lfloor \frac{t}{2^{r-1}} \right\rfloor \left\lfloor \frac{q}{2^{r-1}} \right\rfloor & \text{for } n=3, 4, \dots \end{cases}$$

The arranged matrix $[CH(2^n)]$ is obtained from the natural one, $[CH_0(2^n)]$ after rearranging its rows in such a way, that the number of sign changes for the elements in the row q to be increased by one in the next row, $(q+1)$. The coefficients of the matrix $[S_0(2^n)]$, are:

$$[11] \quad s_0(u, v) = \sum_{i=0}^{2^n-1} \sum_{k=0}^{2^n-1} B(i, k) e^{-j\frac{\pi}{2}(ui+vk)} h_0(u, i) h_0(v, k) \text{ for } u, v = 0, 1, \dots, 2^n - 1,$$

where $B(i, k)$ is the element of the original image $[B(2^n)]$. For the calculation of coefficients $s(u, v)$, obtained using the matrix $[CH(2^n)]$, is necessary to rearrange coefficients $s_0(u, v)$. Each complex coefficient $s_0(u, v)$ is then represented as:

$$[12] \quad s_0(u, v) = s_{0, Re}(u, v) - js_{0, Im}(u, v) = M_0(u, v) e^{-j\varphi_0(u, v)}, \text{ where:}$$

$$[13] \quad s_{0, Re}(u, v) = \sum_{i=0}^{2^n-1} \sum_{k=0}^{2^n-1} B(i, k) h_0(u, i) h_0(v, k) \cos\left[\frac{\pi}{2}(ui + vk)\right],$$

$$[14] \quad s_{0, Im}(u, v) = \sum_{i=0}^{2^n-1} \sum_{k=0}^{2^n-1} B(i, k) h_0(u, i) h_0(v, k) \sin\left[\frac{\pi}{2}(ui + vk)\right].$$

From all spectrum coefficients are chosen the complex-conjugated couples $s(u, v)$ and $s^*(u, v)$ (with phases $\varphi(u, v) = -\varphi^*(u, v)$ and modules $|M(u, v)| = |M^*(u, v)|$). Every consecutive bit $w_r(p)$ of the watermark data p is inserted in the phases of coefficients $s(u, v)$ and $s^*(u, v)$ only, in correspondence with the relation:

$$[15] \quad \varphi_{w_r(p)}(u, v) = -\varphi_{w_r(p)}^*(u, v) = \begin{cases} \varphi(u, v) + \Delta, & \text{if } w_r(p) = 1; \\ \varphi(u, v) - \Delta, & \text{if } w_r(p) = 0. \end{cases}$$

Here $\varphi_{w_r(p)}(u, v)$ and $\varphi_{w_r(p)}^*(u, v)$ are the phases of the watermarked coefficients $s_{w_r(p)}(u, v)$ and $s_{w_r(p)}^*(u, v)$. The watermark data is represented by the binary sequence $w_r(p)$ for $r = 1, 2, \dots, R$ (R is the number of the watermark binary elements). The parameter Δ is the angle, which defines the watermark "depth", "transparency" and the resistance against pirates' attacks. The sequence of bits $w_r(p)$ is obtained after performing operation "XOR" both for each bit of the watermark and the corresponding bit from a pseudorandom sequence, which represents a secret

(private) or public key, used for the watermark encryption. In this case the autocorrelation function of the sequence $w_r(p)$ is chosen to be of the kind “delta-pulse”. This ensures high accuracy for the watermark detection and extraction. In case that the currently processed complex spectrum coefficient, which should be watermarked, has zero amplitude, the corresponding binary value of the watermark is omitted and the binary symbol from the pseudorandom sequence only remains, because “XOR” is not applied. In result, the errors in the extracted watermark elements are reduced, because the spectrum coefficients of zero amplitude have zero phases as well, and they are practically not suitable for watermark elements extraction.

The coefficients of the rearranged spectrum matrix $[S_w(2^n)]$ are:

$$[16] \quad s_{w_r(p)}(u,v) = M(u,v) e^{-j\varphi_{w_r(p)}(u,v)}$$

The matrix $[S_w(2^n)]$ is processed with inverse 2D-CHT and as a result is obtained:

$$[17] \quad [B_w(2^n)] = 4^{-n} [CH(2^n)]^* [S_w(2^n)] [CH(2^n)]^*,$$

where $[CH(2^n)]^* = 2^n [CH(2^n)]^{-1}$.

The pixels of the watermarked image are defined by the relation:

$$[18] \quad B_w(i,k) = \sum_{u=0}^{2^n-1} \sum_{v=0}^{2^n-1} s_w(u,v) e^{j\frac{\pi}{2}(ui+vk)} h_0(u,i) h_0(v,k) \text{ for } i, k = 0, 1, \dots, 2^n-1.$$

3.2 Fragile watermark insertion

The IPD decomposition permits insertion of information in the processed image, which is an additional decomposition layer. This could be any image, overlaid on the processed decomposition level, which prevents the visualization for the corresponding approximation. The removal of the fragile “hiding” watermark is carried out using a password.

3.3 Watermark Detection

For the watermark detection in unknown image are performed Eqs. [11-14], presented above. First, should be checked whether in the image had been inserted the watermark p , which is one of the known D possible signs. For this is evaluated the mutual correlation $C_{m,p}$ between the m^{th} and p^{th} watermark, the first of which is one of the D possible, and the second is used for watermarking of the complex-conjugated coefficients $s(u,v)$ and $s^*(u,v)$ of the unknown image:

$$[19] \quad C_{m,p} = \sum_{r=1}^R [\varphi(u,v) + \Delta_r(p)] \Delta_r(m) = A(m) + B(p,m) \text{ for } p, m = 1, 2, \dots, D,$$

where D is the number of searched watermarks; $[\varphi(u,v) + \Delta_r(p)] = \varphi_{w_r(p)}(u,v)$ is the phase of the marked spectrum coefficient $s_{w_r(p)}(u,v)$ of the matrix $[S_w(2^n)]$, which contains the p^{th} watermark data;

$$[20] \quad \Delta_r(p) = (-1)^{w_r(p)} \Delta = \begin{cases} +\Delta & \text{if } w_r(p) = 1; \\ -\Delta & \text{if } w_r(p) = 0, \end{cases}$$

$$A(m) = \varphi(u,v) \sum_{r=1}^R \Delta_r(p) \approx 0 \text{ for } R \gg 1, \quad B(p,m) = \sum_{r=1}^{R_p} \Delta_r(p) \Delta_r(m).$$

In case that spectrum coefficients are not marked, $\Delta_r(p) = 0$ and $C_{m,b} \approx 0$; else:

$$[21] \quad C_{m,p} \approx \begin{cases} \sum_{r=1}^R [\Delta_r(m)]^2 = R\Delta^2 & \text{if } m = p; \\ \sum_{r=1}^R \Delta_r(m)\Delta_r(p) \approx 0 & \text{if } m \neq p. \end{cases}$$

The decision for the detection of the watermark data p is:

$$[22] \quad p = \begin{cases} \text{Yes, if } [C_{m,p}/R\Delta^2] \geq \theta; & \text{for } m, p = 1, 2, \dots, D, \\ \text{No, - in other cases.} \end{cases}$$

where θ is a pre-defined threshold in the range $0 < \theta < 1$.

The so described **watermark detection** is “blind”, i.e. it does not need the original image. For the **watermark extraction** is needed the original image. It is supposed, that the owner is the person, authorized to do this. After the phase spectrums of the original and the watermarked images had been calculated, the phases of the corresponding coefficients are subtracted and is defined the sequence, obtained after applying the “XOR” function on the watermark and the pseudorandom sequence, which is the encryption key. The watermark is obtained after performing “XOR” for the phase differences sequences and the key.

4 Database Management Based on the IPD Decomposition

The layered approach for image archiving, based on the IPD decomposition, permits to develop flexible software tools for image database management. The main idea is that any image in the database is visualized layer by layer with increasing resolution. The visualization starts with the coarse approximation of the archived image, which corresponds to the low decomposition layer. The next approximation (of higher quality) is visualized only in case that the user has a password. Together with the better quality, the system reveals on request (and if password is available) additional personal information. In case, that the image (or a part of it, containing certain ROI) is hidden under a fragile watermark, it is visualized together with the watermark, which could be removed only if the password for the corresponding decomposition level is provided.

The image preparation for image database with layered access is shown on Fig. 1. The image is archived layer by layer and the watermarks are inserted together with the image processing. The ROI (if there is one in the image) is processed in such a way, that to permit direct access for authorized users (separate pyramid is developed for the ROI representation). The structure of the hierarchical access to the image database contents is shown on Fig. 2.

5 Conclusions

The proposed method for creation of medical databases and image content protection, based on the IPD, offers various tools for image processing and archiving. The general part of the database information could be used for various applications: students learning, disease description, disease history and treatment, statistics, information exchange, etc. The main advantages of the new method are:

- It permits flexible layered access to the archived information, depending on the user authorization;
- It offers reliable content protection with multiple resistant and fragile watermarks, inserted in the consecutive decomposition levels;

- The layered approach for image processing permits the creation of general models for object description and representation. In the case, when RST-invariant transformations are used (for example, the 2D Mellin-Fourier transform) the objects representation is RST-invariant as well;
- The method modification permits the description to be contrast-invariant as well (Kountchev et al, 2010);
- The proposed database management corresponds to the contemporary methods for content- and context-based data search;
- The method permits layered object search in image databases, similar with human way for object recognition (starting from slight similarity and continuing up to higher similarity and sure identification).
- The proposed method has big potential for future investigations in the area of invariant object representation and efficient search in large image databases.

Fig. 1. Multi-layer image archiving and content protection

Fig. 2. Hierarchical DB access

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